

GUANYLALKYLUREAS AND THEIR METALLIC COMPLEXES. PART IV. INSTABILITY CONSTANTS OF COPPER AND NICKEL COMPLEXES

BY R. L. DUTTA

Instability constants of the copper and nickel complexes of guanylurea, guanylmethylurea and guanylethylurea have been determined from a study of their formation reactions by means of spectrophotometric measurements. The copper guanylurea complexes like the copper biguanide complexes are found to be formed in two successive steps: (1) a deep blue *mono*-guanylurea complex and (2) a rose-red *bis*-guanylurea complex. The formation of the nickel *bis*-guanylurea complexes on the other hand takes place in a single step. The guanylalkylurea complexes have been found to be far more stable than those of guanylurea.

A study of the synthesis of guanylalkylureas and the preparation of the copper and nickel complexes of these reagents have been recorded in the earlier parts of this series (this *Journal*, 1959, 36, 499, 567, 576). It has been observed therein that the guanylalkylureas give rise to stable complexes with copper and nickel ions, which unlike the complex bases of the parent ligand do not decompose when their aqueous or aqueous-alcoholic solutions are boiled.

With a view to determining the stability of these complexes, a physico-chemical examination of the copper and nickel complexes of guanylmethylurea and of guanylethylurea was undertaken. Due to insolubility of the copper and nickel complexes of the guanyl-(*n* & *iso*)butyl and of guanylhexylurea in water, these were found unsuitable for physico-chemical measurements in aqueous medium. Qualitative observations in ethanolic medium in which the complexes are soluble, however, showed that the pH range of their formation was almost the same as that for the guanylmethylurea and guanylethylurea complexes. For the purpose of comparison the copper complex of the parent ligand, simple guanylurea, was also studied. The nickel complex of guanylurea could not be examined as the complex is known only in the form of its insoluble base (cf. Rây and Bandopadhyay, this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 865).

The acid dissociation constants of guanylurea, guanylmethyl-, -ethyl-, -butyl-, -amyl- and -hexyl-ureas have been determined following the method of Bjerrum ("Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solution", P. Haase and Sons, Copenhagen, 1941; cf. Das Sarma, this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 217).

In solution guanylalkylureas may be present in three forms: GauH , GauH_2^+ and GauH_3^{2+} depending on the acidity of the medium. In low acid concentration it occurs mostly as GauH_2^+ , the concentration of GauH_3^{2+} ion being negligible. Therefore:

$$k_{a1} = \frac{[\text{GauH}] [\text{H}^+]}{[\text{GauH}_2^+]} \text{ and } k_{a2} = \frac{[\text{GauH}_2^+] [\text{H}^+]}{[\text{GauH}_3^{2+}]}$$

Measurements were made with a low concentration of the reactants in presence of 0.1M-KCl for maintaining a constant ionic strength.

The values of k_{a1} and k_{a2} were obtained from the formation curves traced by plotting $\bar{\eta}$ against the pH values (Fig. 1), when $\bar{\eta} = 0.5$ and 1.5 respectively.

The values of the first acid dissociation constant (k_{a_1}) of guanylurea is of the order of 10^{-9} while that of the guanyllalkylureas is of the order of 10^{-11} . This indicates that guanylurea is far weaker as a base than the guanyllalkylureas, which again are somewhat weaker than biguanide and substituted biguanides ($k_{a_1} \approx 10^{-12}$).

FIG. 1

Acid dissociation constant of guanylureas.

A. Guanylurea. B. Guanylmethylurea.

ethylurea hydrochloride. The peak in the Job's curve (optical density against mole fraction of the reagent) corresponds to a composition of 1:1. A similar experiment, however, could not be carried out in the case of simple guanylurea, as at the comparatively high pH of its formation (above 6.0) it was found difficult to avoid precipitation of copper hydroxide in the solution with smaller reagent concentration. A few of these blue copper *mono*-guanyllalkylurea complexes have been isolated, and their properties studied (vide Part II, *loc. cit.*). With increasing pH the blue colour gradually changed to red-violet. This red-violet solution showed its absorption maximum in the region 530-540 $m\mu$ (Fig. 2). The formation of this coloured complex was complete at a pH 6.8 for guanylmethylurea and guanylethylurea, but for the unsubstituted guanylurea it required a higher pH of 7.5. Molar extinction coefficients were therefore obtained from the optical density of solutions at 660 $m\mu$ for the *mono*-complex and at 540 $m\mu$ for the *bis*-complex at the optimum pH of their formation.

Copper-guanyllalkylurea System

A series of solutions containing copper chloride and guanyllalkylurea hydrochloride in the molar ratio of about 1:4 (*i.e.*, in excess over the stoichiometric values for the formation of the *bis*-complex) were adjusted to different pH values. On increasing the pH of the system the green colour of the initial solution turned deep blue. The formation of the blue colour was found to be complete at pH 4.0. The unsubstituted guanylurea was also found to form a blue copper complex at pH above 6.0, but only in the presence of a larger concentration of the ligand (1:8). The blue complex gives an absorption maximum in the region of 650-660 $m\mu$. This corresponds to the formation of a copper *mono*-guanylurea complex as established by Job's method of continued variation between equimolecular solutions of cupric chloride and guanylmethylurea or guanylethylurea hydrochloride.

FIG. 2

Absorption spectra of Cu & Ni guanylmethylurea chlorides.

A. Copper *mono*-guanylmethylurea chloride (0.00496 *M*).
 B. Copper *bis*-guanylmethylurea chloride (0.00248 *M*).
 C. Nickel *bis*-guanylmethylurea chloride (0.002445 *M*).

These spectrophotometric studies reveal the formation of the copper complexes in two stages: (1) the first step involves an equilibrium between aquo-cupric ion or rather chlorocupric ion and copper *mono*-guanylurea, and (2) the second between copper *mono*-guanylurea and copper *bis*-guanylurea.

It may be noted here that measurements could not be made in solutions containing perchlorate or nitrate anions as the corresponding complex copper salts were precipitated. All experiments were therefore carried out at a constant ionic strength of 0.1M-KCl, and using copper chloride. A higher concentration of KCl resulted in the salting out of the complex chlorides. Absorption due to any chloro-cupric ion was, however, ignored at the concentration of the chloride ion employed. A critical discussion on this point has been made by Ray and Rây (this *Journal*, 1959, 36, 849).

Nickel-guanylalkylurea System

Unlike copper complex, the formation of nickel guanylalkylurea complex occurred in a single stage. The absorption peak of the nickel *bis*-guanylalkylurea lies at 440-450 m μ at pH 6.0, when the solution turns orange-yellow (Fig. 2). For guanylmethylurea and guanylethylurea the formation of the nickel complex was complete above pH 7.4. Molar extinction coefficients were evaluated at 440 m μ from the optical density at pH 7.4.

The concentration of any coloured species (A or B) in a system in equilibrium can be calculated from the following equation (cf. Ray and Rây, *loc cit.*):

$$C_A = \frac{D - \epsilon_B C}{\epsilon_A - \epsilon_B}; C = C_A + C_B$$

where ϵ and C signify respectively the molar extinction coefficients and concentrations of the coloured species, and D , the optical density.

Instability Constants

Copper Complexes.— For copper the system gives rise to the complexes $[\text{Cu}(\text{GauH})]^{2+}$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{GauH})_2]^{2+}$, depending on the pH of the mixture.

The equilibrium constants for these two reactions are given by:

$$kf_1' = \frac{[\text{Cu}(\text{GauH})]^{2+} [\text{H}^+]}{[\text{Cu}^{2+}] [\text{GauH}_2^+]}, \text{ and } kf_2' = \frac{[\text{Cu}(\text{GauH})_2]^{2+} [\text{H}^+]}{([\text{Cu}(\text{GauH})]^{2+}) (\text{GauH}_2^+)}$$

The evaluation of kf_1' and kf_2' from the optical density measurements was made as follows:

Let α = total metal, β = total guanylurea, C_1 = conc. of the *mono*-complex $[\text{Cu}(\text{GauH})]^{2+}$, and C_2 = conc. of the *bis*-complex $[\text{Cu}(\text{GauH})_2]^{2+}$. Therefore,

$$kf_1' = \frac{C_1 \times [\text{H}^+]}{(\alpha - C_1) [\text{GauH}_2^+]}, \text{ and } kf_2' = \frac{C_2 \times [\text{H}^+]}{(\alpha - C_2) [\text{GauH}_2^+]}$$

The concentration of GauH_2^+ was calculated from a knowledge of the acid dissociation constants of guanylureas in a manner similar to that of the biguanides (cf. Ray and Rây, *loc. cit.*). Thus

$$\text{and } kf_1' = \frac{C_1 \times [\text{H}^+]}{(\alpha - C_1) (\beta - C_1)} \left\{ 1 + \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{k_{a2}} \right\}$$

$$kf_2' = \frac{C_2 [\text{H}^+]}{(\alpha - C_2) (\beta - \alpha - C_2)}$$

The instability constants of the complexes were derived from the following equilibrium reactions :

The successive instability constants are given by

$$K_1 = \frac{[\text{Cu}^{2+}][\text{GauH}]}{[\text{Cu}(\text{GauH})^{2+}]} = \frac{1}{kf_1'} \times k_{a_1}$$

and

$$K_2 = \frac{1}{k_{a_2}'} \times k_{a_1}$$

where k_{a_1} is the first acid dissociation constant of the ligand.

Hence, overall instability constant, $K = k_1 k_2 = \frac{(k_{a_1})^2}{kf_1' \times k_{a_2}'}$.

Nickel Complex.—Nickel reacts with guanylalkylureas in a single step to form the bis-guanylalkylurea complexes.

The equilibrium constant for the reaction is given by :

$$kf' = \frac{[\text{Ni}(\text{GauH})_2^{2+}][\text{H}^+]^2}{[\text{Ni}^{2+}][\text{GauH}_2^+]^2}$$

i.e.

$$kf' = \frac{C_2 [\text{H}^+]^2}{(\alpha - C_2)(\beta - 2C_2)} \quad (\text{vide copper})$$

where C_2 = conc. of nickel complex.

Therefore the instability constant K of the nickel complex is derived from :

and is given by

$$K = \frac{[\text{Ni}^{2+}][\text{GauH}]^2}{[\text{Ni}(\text{GauH}_2)^{2+}]} = \frac{1}{kf'} \times (k_{a_1})^2.$$

The following values for the overall instability constants were thus obtained : copper guanylurea, 6.1×10^{-8} ; copper guanylmethylurea, 1.02×10^{-16} ; copper guanylethylurea, 4.97×10^{-16} ; nickel guanylmethylurea, 5.5×10^{-11} ; nickel guanylethylurea, 1.55×10^{-12} .

Thus it is evident that copper complex of the parent ligand is far less stable as compared to those of the guanylalkylureas, which are close to the biguanide complexes (K of the order of 10^{-18}).

Similarly, the nickel complexes of the guanylalkylureas are also quite stable, the instability constant being a little less than those of the corresponding biguanide complexes (K of the order of 10^{-14}). That the nickel complex of unsubstituted guanylurea is far weaker is shown by the fact that no salt of the complex nickel base could be prepared (Rây and Bandopadhyay, *loc. cit.*).

EXPERIMENTAL

Acid Dissociation Constants of Guanylurea and of Guanylalkylureas

0.05M Guanylurea hydrochloride solution (10 c.c.) was taken in each of several 50 c.c. volumetric flasks along with 5 c.c. of KCl (1M) solution, and these were treated with varying quantities of standard hydrochloric acid or sodium hydroxide solution as was necessary, and the volume made up to the mark. The resulting solutions were allowed to stand at room temperature ($30^\circ \pm 2^\circ$) and the pH values of the solutions were measured next day with a Cambridge pH meter. For pH up to 9, a glass electrode was used and an alkali glass electrode for pH above 9. The values of k_{a_1} and k_{a_2} were obtained from the $\bar{\eta}$ values plotted against pH (Fig. 1).*

* Only a few representative curves have been presented.

TABLE A

	k_{a_1}	k_{a_2}
Guanylurea	6.31×10^{-9}	1.58×10^{-2}
Guanylmethylurea	3.98×10^{-11}	1.34×10^{-3}
Guanylethylurea	0.79×10^{-11}	0.63×10^{-3}
Guanylbutylurea	1.59×10^{-10}	1.26×10^{-3}
Guanylamylurea	5.02×10^{-11}	1.26×10^{-3}
Guanylhexylurea	5.02×10^{-11}	0.56×10^{-3}

Instability Constants of Metal Complexes

Metal chloride solution of known strength and that of the ligand hydrochloride were mixed in the molar ratio (1:4 for the copper complexes and 1:6 for the nickel complexes) in 50 c.c. volumetric flasks. A large excess of the reagent (1:8) had to be used in the case of unsubstituted guanylurea to prevent hydrolysis of its copper complex. The pH values of the solutions were adjusted to different levels by the addition of necessary amount of alkali. KCl was added to maintain a final ionic strength of 0.1M. The pH and the absorption spectra (Uvicam SP 600) of solutions were measured after 6 hrs. The results are recorded in the following tables.

TABLE I

Formation of copper mono-guanylmethylurea (Fig. 3A).

$$\alpha = 0.00496M. \quad \epsilon_{\text{Cu-mono-guanylmethylurea}} = 32.4.$$

$$\beta = 0.01500M. \quad \epsilon_{\text{Cu}^{2+}} = 5.0.$$

KCl = 0.1M. Wave length of measurement = 660 m μ .

pH.	Optical density (1 cm).	C_1 .	$C_0 = \alpha - C_1$ (conc. of free metal),	Non-complexed guanylmethylurea, $x = \beta - C_1$.	$x = \text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{2+}$.	$kf_1' \times 10^6$.
3.10	0.050	0.000920	0.004040	0.014080	0.008360	2.046
3.20	0.058	0.001211	0.003750	0.013769	0.009376	2.181
3.30	0.070	0.001650	0.003310	0.013350	0.009716	2.571
3.40	0.078	0.001941	0.003020	0.013059	0.010070	2.541
3.50	0.088	0.002307	0.002653	0.012693	0.010270	2.683
3.60	0.100	0.002744	0.002216	0.012256	0.010330	3.007
3.70	0.108	0.003036	0.001924	0.011964	0.010410	3.024
3.80	0.116	0.003330	0.001630	0.011670	0.010440	3.113

$$kf_1' \text{ (average)} = 2.646 \times 10^{-2}.$$

$$k_1 = 1.504 \times 10^{-9}.$$

TABLE II

Formation of copper bis-guanylmethylurea (Fig. 3B).

$$\alpha = 0.00248M. \quad \epsilon_{\text{Cu-bis-guanylmethylurea}} = 43.4.$$

$$\beta = 0.01000M. \quad \epsilon_{\text{Cu-mono-guanylmethylurea}} = 12.1.$$

KCl = 0.1M. Wave length of measurements = 540 m μ .

pH.	Optical density (1 cm).	C_2 .	C_1 .	$x = \text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{2+}$.	$kf_2' \times 10^6$.
5.40	0.065	0.001119	0.001361	0.006411	5.105
5.50	0.070	0.001278	0.001202	0.006242	5.387
5.60	0.075	0.001438	0.001042	0.006082	5.701
5.70	0.079	0.001566	0.000914	0.005954	5.742
5.80	0.083	0.001693	0.000787	0.005827	5.852
5.90	0.088	0.001853	0.000626	0.005668	6.575
6.00	0.091	0.001949	0.000531	0.005571	6.588

$$kf_2' \text{ (average)} = 5.85 \times 10^{-4}.$$

$$k_2 = 6.803 \times 10^{-9}.$$

$$\text{Overall instability constant} = k_1 \cdot k_2 = 1.02 \times 10^{-14}.$$

TABLE III

Formation of nickel bis-guanylmethylurea (Fig. 3,C).

$\alpha = 0.002445M$. $\epsilon_{Ni \text{ bis-guanylmethylurea}} = 55.2$.

$\beta = 0.01500M$. $\epsilon_{Ni^{2+}} = 1.0$.

KCl = 0.1M. Wave length of measurements = 440 m μ .

pH.	Optical density (1 cm).	C_2 (complex).	$C_0 = \alpha - C_2$ (conc. of free metal).	$x = CuH_2^{2+}$ (free guanylmethylurea).	$kf'_x \times 10^{11}$.
7.00	0.044	0.000767	0.001678	0.013466	2.52
7.10	0.056	0.000988	0.001457	0.013024	2.52
7.20	0.071	0.001265	0.001180	0.012470	2.74
7.30	0.085	0.001524	0.000921	0.011952	2.90
7.40	0.102	0.001837	0.000608	0.011326	3.73

kf' (average) = 2.88×10^{-11} .

Instability constant $K = 5.5 \times 10^{-11}$.

FIG. 3

Formation curves of Cu & Ni guanylmethylurea chlorides.

- A. Copper mono-guanylmethylurea ($Cu^{2+} = 0.00496 M$).
 B. Copper bis-guanylmethylurea ($Cu^{2+} = 0.00248 M$).
 C. Nickel bis-guanylmethylurea ($Ni^{2+} = 0.002445 M$).

Similar measurements with guanylurea and guanylethylurea gave the following results for the instability constants of their copper and nickel complexes.

TABLE IV

	kf'_1 .	k_1 .	kf'_2 .	k_2 .	K .
Copper guanylurea	8.00×10^{-5}	7.857×10^{-6}	8.13×10^{-4}	7.76×10^{-4}	6.1×10^{-8}
Copper guanylethylurea	3.773×10^{-2}	2.094×10^{-10}	3.33×10^{-4}	2.372×10^{-6}	4.97×10^{-18}
Nickel guanylethylurea	4.018×10^{-11} (kf')	..	..	..	1.55×10^{-22}

Author's grateful thanks are due to Prof. P. Rây for his kind advice and interest in this work.